

APPEARANCE OF REFLECTION AT DIFFERENT PERIODS OF PERSONAL DEVELOPMENT

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7634156>

Annotation. Article consider aspects of occurrence of reflection in different stages of personal development. Moreover, there are cases on development of reflection in different age periods. Especially, there have been shown particular qualities of development of reflection from pre-school age to teenage period.

Key words: reflection, pre-school age, thought, egocentrism, speech, identification, personal qualities, "I" image, primary school age, teenage period, personal reflection, sensitive period

Аннотация. Мақолада шахс ривожланишининг турли босқичларида рефлексияни намоён бўлишининг ўзига хос жиҳатлари асослаб берилган. Шунингдек, турли ёш даврларида рефлексияни тараққий этиши билан боғлиқ масалалари изоҳланган. Айниқса, рефлексияни ривожланиши мактабгача тарбия ёшидан бошланиб, то ўспиринлик давригача давом этиши ҳамда намоён бўлишининг характерли хусусиятлари кўрсатиб ўтилган.

Калит сўзлар: рефлексия, мактабгача тарбия ёши, тафаккур, эгоцентризм, нутқ, идентификация, шахс сифатлари, "Мен" образи, кичик мактаб ёши, ўспиринлик даври, ўспиринлик ёши, шахсий рефлексия, сензитив давр.

Аннотация. В статье основывается особенности проявления рефлексии в разных этапах жизни личности. К тому же поясняется вопросы связанные с развитием рефлексии в разных этапах жизни личности. В особенности выражается характерные свойства рефлексии которые начинаются в дошкольном возрасте и продолжаются до подросткового возраста.

Ключевые слова: рефлексия, дошкольный возраст, интеллект, эгоцентризм, речь, идентификация, личностные свойства, образ «Я», младший школьный возраст, подростковый возраст, личная рефлексия, сензитивный период.

To fully understand the psychological nature of the concept of reflection, it is important to know its genesis. At this point, when does a person have the ability to reflect for the first time? What is embodied as its primary object? What factors affect the development of the reflexive nature of human thinking? a legitimate question arises. Therefore, it is appropriate to first explain the meaning of the concept of reflection. In particular, reflection is shown as a

mental process aimed at self-awareness, understanding, analysis of one's actions, behavior, speech, experience, feelings, situations, character's attitude towards oneself and others, tasks, assignments, in general.

It is known that, according to psychological researches, reflection can be observed in children of preschool age. Undoubtedly, reflexes are not evident in children of this age. J. Piaget's ideas about the phenomenon of egocentrism and egocentric speech of children's thinking can be seen as a confirmation of this opinion, that is, its psychological essence is the child's inability to coordinate his point of view with that of others, the inability to decenter.

It is worth noting that reflexive ability expands with new qualities in junior school age. It also consists of finding the content of the need to realize oneself as a person. In contrast to other youth periods, an interest in oneself, in one's inner spiritual life, in the qualities of one's personality arises in a teenager.

As an important factor in its development, it is this educational activity that facilitates the development of intellectual reflection. A new type of reflection begins to appear in the search and sorting of one's own mental actions in the situation of completing educational tasks. Along with the analysis and planning of mental actions, reflection is embodied as a new psychic structure for this age. Studies have shown that intellectual reflection is formed in more than half of students by the end of primary education [2].

Adolescence is an active period for the development of self-awareness. The means of its development is personal reflection. A teenager deepens self-learning by enriching his self-awareness with new material. He studies his personality traits, relationships with others, opportunities and aspirations, strengths and weaknesses. Reflection connects the future and the past, comparing childhood expectations of adult life. The meaningful plan of reflection is very broad, and the teenager analyzes the environment, other people, himself and personal reflection. An important feature of reflection is its rich emotionality. Rapidly changing external appearance, self-perception with others, academic success and abilities are always the focus of reflection and create powerful experiences, as a result of which they themselves are reflected. Another important feature of adolescent reflection is its free association. A teenager is busy with his mental experiences and thoughts coming from different directions under the influence of the external situation. However, in the center of the reflection is his own, that is, his personality. It is in reflection that he satisfies his need for self-identification, which interests him more than

anything else. A teenager tries to understand the "I", "Who am I?" finding an answer to the question is the main problem of this period.

Obviously, reflexive abilities are not the same in all teenagers. The intensity and breadth of reflection during adolescence is directly related to the influence of factors such as family upbringing, family traditions, reading and discussing good books, being attentive to other people's thoughts and experiences, and being amazed by the creation of the universe. However, a characteristic condition common to all adolescents - given to them by nature - is the ability to raise oneself to a higher level spiritually in a short period of time.

Adolescence is a short period from adolescence to adulthood, and its age range includes the period from 15-16 to 21-25 years. It is in adolescence that the formation of a person as a person and a citizen takes place. Without exaggeration, it can be said that it is the period of the second birth of a person.

The most important spiritual task of adolescence is the process of personal and professional self-realization. The teenager tries to form an internal position (status) in relation to himself and others (Who am I?, Why do I live?, Who can I be in life?). During adolescence, the problem of choosing life values is very strong. It is in the period of adolescence that he understands the categories of good and evil, honor and shame, rights and obligations, and chooses his inner attitude towards life. These problems are the subject of heated arguments for a teenager with his peers and himself. Reflection performs a great spiritual task during adolescence, that is, it is precisely because of it that an important discovery is made - the discovery of one's inner world [4]. Adolescent's developed reflection is polyphonic, it allows to reflect his feelings and experiences, to determine how sincere the relationship of another person is to him. Reflection makes the space of the inner world of the adolescent dynamic, lively, and dramatic. Researcher N.I. Gutkina in his studies on reflection in early adolescence showed that 80% of 9-10 graders have personal reflection. Usually, when moving to a reflexive position (status), conflict situations in communication appear as an important trigger (in 82% of examinees) and become the object of self-analysis of high school students[1].

Reflection is constructive in the social system: it helps determine one's personal status in relation to the outside world. At this age, a person chooses his future development. This is sometimes done through his own spiritual and personal growth, or for material comfort. This competition determines the difference in the value orientation of young people and their ability to reflect. According to its spiritual potential, this age period may not give a person anything in the

development of the ability to reflect. V. S. Mukhina stated that "while living this period, one can become psychologically a teenager"[4].

A sensitive period for the development of reflection is adolescence and adolescence. In the studies devoted to the study of reflexive ability in adults (Tulviste, 1985), it was determined that its further development is a product of a specially organized educational process and may not take place at a rapid pace compared to that of a teenager and adolescent [7]. In other words, over the years, an adult can enrich his intellectual experience with life wisdom. However, this situation is not observed in the reflexive properties of the mind, because the automatic development of reflection is not possible [8]. In addition, experience shows that the reflexive tendency of the mind in adolescents becomes more permanent with the passing of years.

In this regard, the question arises, what should be done to maintain and develop such an amazing ability to have an internal dialogue with oneself? Not only common sense, but also research results (Naydenov, 1989; Semenov, 2000) confirm that the only way for reflection to exist in the human mind is cultural richness, an environment full of logical thoughts. It is noted that the progressive change of reflection is to strengthen the permanent stability and appropriateness of reflection of the "self-directedness" of the human mind [5]. Modern literature has a wide range of methods and methods for developing reflection. Below we will think about the effective method of encouraging a person to reflect. "The important key to wisdom is to constantly and frequently ask questions," said the French philosopher Pierre Abelard. Thus, the way to reflection is to ask oneself questions, to answer them, and to analyze both the questions and the answers.

It is clear from the mentioned points that the development of reflection in a person can be inextricably linked with the characteristics of the period. Also, it can be explained by the increased desire to know the place, position, and environment of the person in social life, especially the inner world of oneself. The most important aspect is that the development of reflection in a person ensures the rapid development of the system of self-awareness.

Based on the above considerations, it is appropriate to highlight the following aspects:

- it is observed that the development of reflection takes place in a unique way in different age periods;
- the formation of reflection in junior school age is determined by the formation of egocentric speech and egocentrism;

- emotionality, success and failure in educational activities are considered the main criterion in the development of reflection;
- is characterized by a clear manifestation of personal reflection during adolescence;
- it is noted that the development of reflection during adolescence is related to the system of professional self-awareness in them.

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